

PROFESSIONAL ETHICS AND VALUES IN MANAGEMENT

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Abstract:

Manager draws upon the basic resources which are called 6Ms – men, materials, machines, money, minutes and methods. These six resources are subjected to the management process which consists of typical elements of management or functions of management such as planning, organizing, motivating, leading and controlling of human efforts. Through these managerial functions or management process we can have accomplishments of: The right work, at the right place, At the right time, with the right methods. From such managerial activities we derive the expected results, viz, benefits and satisfaction in individuals, groups, enterprises as well as the society at large. Productivity of all resources in the final analysis depends upon the competency and ability of management of any enterprise to deliver the goods. Thus management will convert disorganized resources of men, money, machines, etc., into useful enterprise. These resources are mobilized, co-ordinated, directed and controlled in such a manner that the enterprise would work towards the realization of common objective. Management provides a dynamic force in getting any enterprise useful activities makes and significant social contributions, for example, customer's needs are met, jobs are created as a result utilizes enjoy higher standard of living. It assures economic growth free from pollution. Government would have income through variety of taxes. Management thus is an invigorating force bringing to life what would otherwise be or potentialities.

Key Words: Management, Government, Benefit, People, Resources, Values, Machine...etc.

Conceptual Analysis of Management:

Management is an exercise in harmonizing men, money, machinery, materials and methods towards fulfilling set of objectives leading to human development, excellent performance, social benefit and global welfare. Man, a conscious being, remains the basic factor in any field of human endeavor. One way to analyze management is to think in terms of what a manager does. Using this approach, we can arrive at the management process which describes the work of any manager. The management work can be divided into a few basic functions of management viz. (1) Planning, (2) Organizing, (3) Leading, (4) Controlling. These concepts are going to explain very lucidly in the coming portion. Management is a universal process in all organized activities. It is not merely confined to factory, shop or office. It is an operative force in all complex organisations trying to achieve some stated objectives. Management is necessary for a business firm, government enterprises, education and health services, business organisations, trade associations and so on. Hence, management skills are transferable and a manager can successfully apply his knowledge and skill in a wide variety of enterprises. Of course, situational factors will influence the suitable combination of managerial skills. Experts agree that management is a distinct activity in any branch of collective human efforts. Similarly, all managerial functions are universal and all managers in any branch of business or non-business activities perform those typical functions of management cycle, viz. Planning, organizing, leading, and controlling. "Management is a multi-purpose organ that manages a business, manages manager, and manages workers and work."¹⁶

Drucker emphasizes three jobs of management: (i) Managing an organization (ii) Managing a manager; and (iii) Managing workers and work. Even if one is omitted, we would not have management any more and we also would not have an enterprise. According to Peter Drucker, it requires the manager to balance and harmonize three major functions of the enterprise. Hence, a manager is a dynamic and life giving element in every organization. Without efficient management we cannot secure best allocation and utilisation of human, material and financial resources. Management is decision-making. Decisions are necessary in all functional areas of any organization. The manager by profession is a decision-maker. All managerial functions are discharged through decision making. All human behaviour involves the problem of choice. The process of making selection is termed as decision making. We have two distinct levels of activity in management: (1) co-ordination and (2) supervision. The co-coordinative function is that of decision making - the process of selecting an action from the alternative courses of action. Management in the co-ordination sense is the central concept of management theory. Decision-making is the core of the process of management. In short, decision making pervades all managerial functions. This definition ignores the function of supervision and leadership. "Management is the process of designing and maintaining an environment, working together in group to efficiently accomplish selected aims."¹⁷

According to this definition management is an art of creating performance environment enabling the group to attain stated objectives and management is the body of organized knowledge, *i.e.*, science which underlines the art. Creation of managerial environment for joint efforts of people working in an organisation in order to accomplish planned objectives demands intelligent application of management knowledge to numerous and varied practical problems so that we can have the best results under the given situation or realities.

Definition of Management:

"Management is a distinct ongoing process of allocating inputs of an organization (human and economic resources) by typical managerial functions (planning, organizing, leading and controlling) for the purpose of achieving stated objectives. *viz.*, output of goods and services desired by its customers (environment). In the process, work is performed with and through the personnel of the organization in an ever changing environment."¹⁸ "Management is a social process involving co-ordination of human and material resources through the functions of planning, organizing, staffing, leading and controlling in order to accomplish stated objectives."¹⁹

The Concept of the Management:

Management is a central directing and controlling agency indispensable for any enterprise involving organized co-operation and requiring collective efforts to realize some common desired results or specific objectives. The group efforts in the pursuit of common goals and objectives require proper leadership which is provided by the management. Management has three distinct meanings.

Management as a Process:

This describes an activity, which can be better described by the word managing. Under this concept we consider activity by means of which scarce resources are combined to achieve given ends. Manager draws upon the basic resources which are called 6Ms – men, materials, machines, money, minutes and methods. These six resources are subjected to the management process which consists of typical elements of management or functions of management such as planning, organizing, motivating, leading and controlling of human efforts. Through these managerial functions or management process we can have accomplishments of: (1) The right work (2) At the right place. (3) At the right time, and (4) with the right methods. From such managerial activities we derive the expected results, *viz.* benefits and satisfaction in individuals, groups, enterprises as well as the society at large. Productivity of all resources in the final analysis depends upon the competency and ability of management of any enterprise to deliver the goods. Thus management will convert disorganized resources of men, money, machines, etc., into useful enterprise. These resources are mobilized, co-coordinated, directed and controlled in such a manner that the enterprise would work towards the realization of common objective. Management provides a dynamic force in getting any enterprise useful activities makes and significant social contributions, for example, customer's needs are met, jobs are created as a result utilizes enjoy higher standard of living. It assures economic growth free from pollution. Government would have income through variety of taxes. Management thus is an invigorating force bringing to life what would otherwise be or potentialities. Mental poise and balanced temperament can be developed by building up strong character reflecting the basic human and ethical values. This state of mind is needed to cope with the inevitable stress and strain arising in your day-to-day life. Thus, when values and skills are combined by a manager and workers, the management of organization will be much better. There would be smooth interaction with people. The management of stress will be easier. The quality of life and the quality of work would be enhanced. Mind-stilling exercises will also enrich life of an organization. (b) Managers: The term management may refer to those who are carrying the activity of management, *viz.*, the managers are thereto manage an organization, and who manage the workers and the work. In a large organization, we have different levels of management. The top management, *i.e.* managerial agencies at the top is the governing board of directors, which is the supreme policy-making and decision making authority. The managing director, the chief executive or the executive directors are the heads of major divisions. These constitute the top management. The middle management group consists of middle managers *i.e.*, departmental managers, and subordinate officers who work under the heads of the departments and who enjoy delegated authorities from their bosses. The flow of authority or power is always downward, flowing from the top to the bottom and this is brought about by proper delegation. Manager himself can do nothing. He cannot produce goods. He has to multiply his personality particularly in a big organization and this is done through delegation of authority. Hence, many a time management is defined as that agency which gets things done through people. This definition points out the importance of delegation and motivation management. This definition also implies decision making process as an integral part of management. Delegation transfers steadily the decision making power from the higher level to the lower level. Under the middle management group, we have low level managers such as supervisors, foremen who are directly in charge of the operatives, *i.e.*, rank and file of workers. Lower level managers, middle managers and top managers are many a time called management as distinguished from labour, *viz.*; the operators or workers. At present greater empowerment of workers is also expected.

Special Field of Study:

Profession, the third concept of management points out that it is a body of knowledge about the

activity of managing the process of management and this body of knowledge is usually regarded as a special field (study, *i.e.*, profession). The third concept of management as a profession is due to the managerial revolution which took place since 1960. In a joint stock company there will be a complete separation of management from ownership. Shareholders are owners of the enterprise. They do not have management rights and we have a small body of executives representing professional managers to whom the work of management is entrusted. Under a corporate personality, management has emerged as a separate entity and it reveals the professional character of management, *i.e.*, management by salaried experts. "A professional manager is one who specializes in the work of planning, organizing, leading and controlling the efforts of others and does so through systematic use of classified knowledge, a common vocabulary and principles and who subscribes to the standards of practice and code of ethics established by recognized body."²⁰ Managerial revolution has brought about separation of management from ownership in corporate management in all countries slowly but steadily. Hence, management is assuming professional character during the last three decades. Code of conduct makes enlightened businessmen recognize that management is a social institution and it has social responsibilities to be fulfilled towards customers, employees, and the public or community. Corporations have now social conscience and awareness. Social-oriented marketing concept is a reflection of corporate code of conduct.

Importance of Management:

At all levels of organization in any joint enterprise (requiring teamwork) managing is an essential input. Management is the most critical asset for the success of any enterprise. Management can deliver rising standards of living and standard of life to the society. It can offer enriched life to employees, consumers and citizens or members of a community. It assures smooth running of an enterprise. It is a powerful innovative force. It is the main determinant of our economic progress. It is the guide for our effective government. It can strengthen our nation. Specialists of economic development have pointed out to the governments of developing countries that even the most modern technology with best materials, resources and plant facilities together with liberal and cheap finance may not be able to achieve stated objectives (industrial productivity and quality of working life) without effective and efficient management. The greatest obstacle and the limiting factor for undeveloped and developing countries is the quality of management. Competent managerial personnel were really responsible for the accelerated development and recovery of Germany and Japan after the World War II after 1950. Good management is the only economic resource which can decide the extent of utilization of all other resources. It alone is responsible for the optimum utilization of available scarce resources. Productivity of resources is the current burning problem in all countries. Problem of inflation and ever growing consumer demand due to growth of population have created unique importance to productivity. Management is called upon to meet the challenge of productivity. Managers have to manage separately the productivity of all four key resources: capital, crucial physical resources, time and labour (skilled people, wisdom people, managerial and professional people). But what matters in the end is the total, overall productivity of an enterprise, for example, factory, store, bank, hospital, school, office and so on. Managers must commit themselves to accomplish steady increase in productivities of all resources particularly in turbulent and ever changing environment. Good management recognizes immense potential energy of human resources. Human resources are more productive than material resources. Good management brings out this potential energy. Good management is necessary in industry, commerce, agriculture, hospital, educational, institution, sports, charitable institution, political bodies, trade unions and Government. In the field of co-operation, small and cottage industries, we need good management. Government is the greatest industrialist and greatest employer in India. Hence, management has gained greatest importance in all government branches of administration.

Outlining the Basic Functions of Management:

"Management is what management does"²¹ points out the functional approach to management and emphasises the importance of distinctive managerial functions which together give us unified concept of the process of management. An analysis of the functions of management points out what management does. It also provides the basis for defining precisely the word 'management'. Broadly speaking, a manager is called upon to perform the following managerial functions: (1) Planning, (2) Organizing, (3) Staffing, (4) Leading, (5) Motivating, (6) Controlling, (7) Co-coordinating, and (8) Communicating. Some authors since they include working staff as part of within the organisation and consider co-coordinating and communicating as vital part of motivation and leadership. The sequence of manager's functions begins with planning. However, a manager performs all six functions simultaneously or several times during the working day. Leading, motivating, co-coordinating, and communicating constitute enacting management-in-action.

(a) Planning:

When management is reviewed as a process, planning is the first function performed by a manager. The work of a manager begins with the setting of objectives of the organization and goals in each area of the business. This is done through planning. Manager probes the present to find out where he is and he then forecasts future objectives, which will indicate where he wants to be, *i.e.*, the destination to be reached. The alternatives to achieve the objectives are evaluated and the selected alternative becomes the plan of action. Through taking purposeful action regarding the company's major asset, the manager assumes the first

managerial function i.e., planning. Rather than managing somehow, he plans in advance the future course of action on the basis of facts and figures about the opportunities to be capitalized and threats to overcome in the near future. A plan is a predetermined course of action to accomplish the set objectives. It is today's projection for tomorrow's activity. Once the plan is formulated, the manager has to indicate the objectives of the plan and steps to be taken by his subordinates. By communicating he makes the objects effective. In practice, planning function is all-pervading. It is involved in organization, leading, motivating, and controlling. Budget is a part of planning as well as an instrument of control. Planning makes things happen that would not otherwise occur. Planning involves developing objectives, strategies, policies, procedures, programmed, etc. As it involves making choices, decision-making is the heart of planning.

(b) Organizing:

Managing a business is not just planning. It includes putting life into the plan by bringing together the executive personnel, workers, capital, machinery, materials, physical facilities and other things or services to execute the plans. When these resources are assembled the enterprise comes to life. Organizing involves determining activities needed to fulfill the objectives, grouping these activities into manageable units or departments, and assigning such groups of activities to managers. Delegation of authority creates an organization. It determines authority responsibility relationship. These relationships must be properly co-ordinated to secure unity of organization. Hence, the work of managing includes both planning and preparing to do, i.e., both planning and organizing. Organizing to achieve the plans is "the tooling process"²² or the preparation for the work to be done. Planning involves thinking, deliberation and decision-making regarding the future course of action. Organizing provides a framework of management or a mechanism for purposive, integrated and co-operative action by many people, in a joint effort to implement any plan. Planning decides what management wants to do, while organizing provides an effective machine for achieving the plan or objectives. Under organizing we have mechanical as well as human aspect. Mechanical aspect provides an organization structure or chart, describing the authority responsibility relationship. Besides formal organization structure, we have also an informal or social organization having an informal group leader, unwritten conventions and code of conduct and the manager has to integrate both these organizations in order to execute the plans and policies.

(c) Staffing:

Staffing involves filling positions needed in the organization structure by appointing competent and qualified persons for the jobs. This needs planning and management of human resources. We have scientific selection, education and training of personnel. We have to provide suitable methods of remuneration and performance appraisal. Much of the work relating to human resource planning and management is delegated to a personnel manager. However, top management is ultimately responsible for all activities relating to staffing.

(d) Leading:

The function of leading has been termed motivating, directing, guiding, teaching, stimulating and actuating. This managerial function is directly concerned with the human factors of an organization. Manager by leadership and motivation has to lead and guide all subordinates and get the work done through people. Leading involves managers, managing workers and the work through the means of motivation, proper leadership, and effective communication as well as coordination. Manager must develop the ability to lead. He must be able to secure willing obedience from his subordinates without destroying their initiative and creativity. The term 'Leading' instead of 'Directing' reflects the trend of modern management philosophy. The reader should always use leading as the basic management function. Leading is the art of influencing people so that they work willingly and enthusiastically in order to achieve group goals.

(e) Motivating:

This managerial function is fully reflected when we define management as the art of getting things done willingly through and with other people. Management is interested in two primary elements: (1) Things, that are material resources and (2) Men and women, that is, human resources. A thing is subject to the laws of mechanics and it is susceptible to scientific or machine like treatment. But human beings cannot be subjected to scientific or machine like treatment. However, through the power of leadership and the science of co-operation, we can evolve a suitable method of integrating the interests of individuals and the organization. Motivating is inseparably intertwined with leadership. The power of management exists with or through people, but never over them, at least in a democratic society. Authority may be imposed from above but it must be supported, nourished and recognized from below, that is, from the subordinates. Then only the authority is meaningful and it can work smoothly. The managerial power has its source in the methods of leading, motivating, appraising, and teaching, influencing, counseling, coaching, delegating and setting an example. So the manager plans, organizes, leads, and motivates the people working with him. Motivation and leadership are the master keys to successful management of any enterprise. They are also-responsible to ensure productivity of human resources. Motivation can set into motion a person to any one certain activity. Motivation assumes unique importance in modern management. Democratic leadership heavily relies on motivation of employees, through inspiration and financial incentives. Human values in industry have accorded special emphasis to this managerial function.

Effective communication and participation enhance the power of motivation. Feedback of information (upward communication) is necessary for effective motivation and leadership. When the job itself is meaningful, interesting and challenging, it can provide maximum motivating power to the employee. Self-motivation from within is preferable for extra-ordinary performance. Satisfaction for accomplishing which is a challenging job becomes the self-administered reward.

(f) Controlling:

Controlling is the last phase of the management process. Control is the process of measuring actual results or present performance, comparing those results to plans or some standard of performance, finding out the reason for deviation of actual from desired result and taking corrective action when necessary. The corrective action may lead to a change in the method of implementation of the plan or change in the plan itself or even a change in the objectives. Usually our desired performance standard is the objectives, policies, programmes, procedures and budgets. A good plan assures effective control. There are three important elements in the total management cycle or system: (1) Planning, (2) Implementation (action) of the plan and (3) Control. The entire planning action-control process in management is repetitive. The control process generates information for modification or even creation of new plans. Planning is followed by action, then by review and control in order to achieve the desired result. Complete operating cycle or planning control cycle includes: (1) Objectives, (2) Planning, (3) Action, (4) Accomplishment, (5) Feedback of Information and (6) Mechanism of Control. Good management adopts this cycle and assures not only survival but also promotes growth. (7). Co-ordination, Each managerial function is an exercise of co-ordination. It is said that co-ordination is the essence of management. It is an integral part of leadership. Co-ordination is concerned with harmonious and unified action directed toward a common objective. It involves inter-relating various parts of the work of organization. It is not a separate activity but a condition that should diffuse itself through all phases of management process. Co-ordination is an orderly arrangement of group efforts to provide unity of action. It ensures that all groups and persons work efficiently, economically and in harmony. Co-ordination can be accomplished automatically if we have sound organization structure. Co-ordination is essential in a large organization because we have: (1) Multiple and complex activities, (2) Complex and elaborate organization structure, (3) Multiple levels of management due to limited span of control, and (4) Acute division of work leading to increasing use of specialists.

A manager must co-ordinate the work for which he is accountable by balancing, timing, and integrating the work. Co-ordination means achieving harmony of individual effort with group effort toward the accomplishment of group objectives. Such efforts of co-ordination are required at all levels of management. Board of directors, managing directors, heads of division and/or departments are the usual agencies of co-ordination to develop an orderly and integrated pattern of group efforts in proper sequence and at proper time. Co-ordination requires effective channels of communication. Person to person communication is most effective for co-ordination. In its broadest sense, communication is the transmission of meaning to others. It means transfer of information and understanding from person to person. A flow of information from the top to the bottom and from the bottom to the top as well as horizontal or linear ways on the same level of organization. In formal communication we have dissemination of information primarily. In inter-personal communication between two or more persons have transmission of information as well as flow of understanding based on two-way traffic of communication. Personal or face-to-face communication is the best form of communication. Managerial leadership depends upon upward communication to the leader in the form of feedback so that he can understand the feelings, emotions, motives and problems of subordinates and his power will have support and acceptance from below. Communication also leads to sharing of information, ideas and knowledge. It enables a group to think together and act together. Society's very existence is dependent upon communication that is, passing of information and understanding from one person to another.

An organization exists on the basis of good system of communication network. A manager spends more than 80 per cent of his time daily on the communication in order to direct, motivate, lead and co-ordinate management activities. When communication breaks down, organized activity also fails. Communication system serves two-fold purposes: (1) can integrate and coordinate all managerial functions as well as all enterprise operations and areas. (2) It links the organization with its environment and enables the enterprise to adapt with all variable forces of the environment. The organization is aware of customer needs, competition, marketing opportunities, threats and risks only through effective system of communication or information. Communication process must have union of values and skills. This will eliminate any tendency to manipulate the devices of communication.

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